

The Effectiveness of Implementing Interactive Training for Teaching Kazakh Language

Samal Abzhanova, Saule Mussabekova

Abstract—Today, a new system of education is being created in Kazakhstan in order to develop the system of education and to satisfy the world class standards. For this purpose, there have been established new requirements and responsibilities to the instructors. Students should not be limited with providing only theoretical knowledge. Also, they should be encouraged to be competitive, to think creatively and critically. Moreover, students should be able to implement these skills into practice. These issues could be resolved through the permanent improvement of teaching methods. Therefore, a specialist who teaches the languages should use up-to-date methods and introduce new technologies. The result of the investigation suggests that an interactive teaching method is one of the new technologies in this field. This paper aims to provide information about implementing new technologies in the process of teaching language. The paper will discuss about necessity of introducing innovative technologies and the techniques of organizing interactive lessons. At the same time, the structure of the interactive lesson, conditions, principles, discussions, small group works and role-playing games will be considered. Interactive methods are carried out with the help of several types of activities, such as working in a team (with two or more group of people), playing situational or role-playing games, working with different sources of information, discussions, presentations, creative works and learning through solving situational tasks and etc.

Keywords—Games, interactive learning, Kazakh language, teaching methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

CURRENTLY, a new system of education which can satisfy world-class standards is being developed in Kazakhstan. For this reason, teachers are expected to show commitment and are given new obligations. Along with the theoretical knowledge, teachers are responsible for developing the creativity of students, for the increase of their competitiveness and for being able to apply that knowledge into practice. These issues will be resolved through the permanent improvement of teaching methods. That is why teachers that specialize in teaching languages should strive to use modern methods and techniques and new technologies as well. The results of comprehensive research show that interactive training method in the field of education is one of the most efficient teaching methods.

Kazakh language plays a very important role in the development of Kazakhstan. Based on this, it would be better to evaluate the effectiveness of interactive training method in teaching Kazakh language. Hopefully, this work will be both

beneficial and interesting for scholars in this area. In translation from English the word "Interactive" means "to work together", "to work in team", the ability to work in interaction with other people ("Interact": "Inter" in team, "act" Action). In other words, interactive teaching is realized through working together, through corporation. This paper considers the interaction between teacher and students and students with other students. The most active students, who discuss issues and make clear and good arguments, win the "competition". In interactive learning students are expected to be active, form their own judgment and express their opinion, prove their point of view, and during the debates they should listen to others, show respect to their opinion.

Interactive methods are carried out through different activities and tasks such as: team work (paired, in groups, all together), research work, situational games and role-playing, discussions, finding information from different sources, giving presentations, completing situational learning tasks and etc.

II. THE PRINCIPLES OF THE CREATION OF INTERACTIVE LESSONS

For now, one of the main principles and purposes of the interactive teaching method is to prepare students psychologically for the interactive learning by paying attention to those who are not ready to actively participate in teamwork because they feel uncomfortable or shy. So there is a need to encourage students to be open and participate actively in lessons and not be shy and quite. This point plays an important role in teaching Kazakh language. Teachers should be responsible for teaching students not only the theoretical knowledge but also for being able to apply those principles and teachings in their daily lives. So, through these method, instructor will teach students to be able to link ideas in a systematic and consistent way. Only in this case, students will be able to implement their theoretical knowledge into practice. From this point of view, the combination of theoretical knowledge and the experience gained through situational games, such as role-playing games, discussions, dialogs with other students, will help to be able to express their points of view without any difficulties [1].

Teaching materials will be held and taught in specific order and logical sequence. When teaching Kazakh language, each topic will be selected through methodical system. Through these method, languages will be taught better in relation to each other. As a result, language materials in any language course will complement each other and simplify the learning process. The specific order mentioned above and the logical sequence of the teaching plan will allow to better control

Samal Abzhanova and Saule Mussabekova are with the Kazakh Language, Literature and Culture Department, Nazarbayev University, Astana, Kazakhstan (e-mail: sabzhanova@nu.edu.kz, smussabekova@nu.edu.kz).

lessons, to check home works and in making revisions. Consistency is very important in this method and that is why it will be guided by the principle of mandatory training in learning of language. Then the students' vocabulary will expand and they will acquire a skill through which they will be able to interact with each other very easily.

In teaching a language the psychological aspect should also be taken into account.

Let us focus on the teaching of Kazakh language and serve it as an example: In order to produce highly educated instructors, we should focus on giving high quality education along with knowledge in human psychology. The teacher should be a psychologist too. The reason why psychology is important here is because any instructor will not be able to teach well his students until he understands their psychology. That is, the instructor will learn and try to understand the character of each individual student, their personal characteristics and their psychology. People learn to think widely when they interact with others [2]. A student goes through three stages in learning a language:

1. The object management. Here, the student learns how to construct sentences that they want to say.
2. Management of others. Here, students work in pairs and learn to check and correct each other
3. Self-management. Students try to express their opinions. This point combines the main three elements of interactive teaching and team works. They are: Teacher, student and the language that will be taught. Team works encourage students to work together without the help of the teacher. In the beginning it might be a little bit difficult for students to work in teams without the help of the teacher, but this method helps them to pay attention to what other members in one team are saying/ doing and to be able to come up with a common answer and correct each other when needed. The effectiveness of working in collaboration with the group is that students learn to pay attention to the partner, to listen to what others are saying. This will affect less active students too. They will try to overcome their shyness, get rid of the uncertainty, and soon will start to enjoy taking part in the group works and will not hesitate to ask questions that they do not understand. In this regard, the group aims to foster co-operation in various psychological games and exercises. To show the importance the psychologist, a scholar Q. Jariqbaev said: "Game is one of the main activities of a child. Various games give children the ability to express and experience the core features of their mental form. A child also practices to behave in public through certain games. For example, any child never plays alone, almost every child plays with their peers, so he or she communicates with other people through the game. These games will encourage the well-development of the abilities of a child. Games in groups influence the formation of a child's moral and aesthetic sense" [3]. Thus, playing games during the language lessons that require language creativity helps students to develop their learning and communication skills.

There are several certain techniques to expand the vocabulary when learning a new language:

Professor Z. Kuzekova [4] classified those techniques in such order:

1. The expansion vocabulary through visual aids;
2. The interpretation of new words through the context;
3. Through looking at synonyms;
4. Through looking at antonyms;
5. Through the analyzing of derived words;
6. Through reading their definitions;
7. Through new word counting (enumeration);
8. Through translating the word into the native language of the learner.

Ways through which the above mentioned techniques will be applied are the following: interactive cluster, chart, target reading, painting, drawing, moving picture, and others. Using the cluster approach the student will develop the ability to think and memorize. An interactive method is a reliable way to success [4]. One of the scholars who study various ways to achieve these communication skills as E. I. Passov said that if a second language is taught according to some factors, then students would be more communicative and eager to study. These factors are:

1. Communication teaching methods;
2. The special exercises;
3. Organization and control of the entire educational process;

These are the main features of this method, such as utilization of communication skills to enhance the educational process. Constantly speaking in the language that is being taught prevents students from thinking that they do not comprehend that language. With such purpose, all exercises should help them to speak more and better. The communicative approach aims to take into account specific points of a student's personal training, including the child's personal qualities. This activity makes children eager to learn the new language. Communicative method requires teachings to be situational, because a natural property is calculated in situational speaking skills. As examined in the works of several previous scholars in the field of language learning, it is known that situational exercises help students a lot to learn and speak the language quicker.

III. INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING SPEAKING

The basic principles of interactive teaching methods are the following ones:

- Lexical (academic, professional vocabulary, careful selection of contingent considerations);
- Role (examining a student through various roles that he/she portray during practical tasks);
- Visual (examining all the students by looking at them and monitoring their performances);
- Self-control (each lesson one of the students in each class takes responsibility to initiate a certain task);
- Multimedia (showing students presentations, slides, films, commercials, video clips and more active use of technology);

- Interactive panel with the help of educational materials; (teachers maintain an active relationship among the group by making constant checkups, the creation of a positive atmosphere among the students during the discussions).

A. The Technology of Interactive Learning

The technology of interactive learning model: practice exercises, games, presentations, discussions, group work, brainstorming, the method of critical thinking, quizzes, mini-studies, business games, role-playing games, training, etc. and now let us focus on the model of technology for teaching on the individual level.

1. **Creative Work** is an educational activity coming from mental, practical and thinking ability of students. The word “create” derives from “create”, “search”, and “design” concepts. Consequently, the invention of something new means to achieve success. Creative tasks, depending on the student's ability and degree of loving the subject should be guided by the requirements for the study. Creative work is an essential part of interactive methods. Creative work (especially practical ones) is to increase an interest of student. Relying on his own or partner's experience, finding a solution to an unknown by himself/herself will increase bounds of cooperation and friendship between students. A choice of creative tasks is a creative task for the teachers. Creative tasks should be as follows:

- Unambiguous answer or solution;
- Be useful for students and be practical;
- Causes interest among students;
- To serve the purpose of learning.

2. **Dispute**. “Discussion” as a method of interactive training was being successfully used in educational institutions of the West. In recent years, it has been used widely in our education system, too. Academic discussions help to expand the topic knowledge of students, increase vocabulary and to speak more coherent.

3. **Work with small groups** gives an opportunity (even for shy students) to participate actively, to cooperate, and to develop communication skills (active listening, coming to a consensus to resolve the contradictions). Mosaics, debates, and other activities are important part of interactive methods for small groups. At the same time working with a group with small number of people require a lot of time.

B. Game as an Interactive Teaching Tool

Game-like lessons help to conduct lessons in interesting and attractive form. Feeling equal, diving into a game assists children to stop being shy, getting rid of psychological obstacles and to overcome fatigue. Let us illustrate game examples. Refreshing games are easy and quickly arouses an interest of language learners. The games consist of exercises, which establish business relationships between student and teacher, and student- student pair. These exercises are like bridges of student transition from activity to activity. By combining the game and learning activities, teacher should

keep inherent nature of the game (joy and pleasure). Also children's knowledge and skills, cognitive abilities should be improved, personal development should be aimed. The game must be played until the end in order to achieve the result.

1. **Business games** first appeared in the field of management, not in the education system. Now business games are used in many areas. The main objectives of the use of business games in education are: increasing student learning will, education, business skills, working on their own, creative thinking, and development of motivation towards studying. Business Games features:

- A business game is determined by the actual beginning time and end time of the game (may be unlimited training time).
- The game is depicted by many factors (one aspect of the situation is considered in training).
- Business games aimed at the formation of multiple skills.
- Business games are known for the following specific content: competition, worsening the interests of the participants.
- In the game someone wins, someone loses.

2. **Role-playing games** enable classes to expand students' horizons, increases learners' interest in the subject. Actions performed by students develop confidence to learn the language. The advantage of role-playing games, every child with access to role will see the true situation, feel and decide. The main task of the instructor is to make student speak. For sure, it is carried out by means of language communication. Role-playing games uses three types of relations:

1. Perceptual. Seeing each other and feeling by intuition.
2. Interactive. People influence each other.
3. Informational. Exchange of views between people, sharing of thoughts and interests, spiritual wealth, and curiosity.

While role-playing games student open their heart, dive into game, show leadership. Role-playing games improves the level of clearly speaking and listening skills and leads to active participation.

The essential requirements of role-playing games:

- The need to enhance the students' interest in the language. In addition, students should choose an appropriate role themselves. Only then, their play and speaking will be clear and convincing.
- Role-playing games should be played in a group.
- More students feel free - more he/she will be interested in playing.

Interpretation of the results of two groups: traditional classroom lessons and lessons using interactive methods show us that the last group improved significantly their lexical and grammatical levels of a language. We can clearly state that the use of different communicative technology based on interactive exercises rises participation of students and overall grade of students in comparison to traditional classroom lessons [5].

Comparing to pre-experiment knowledge level of students, using different tasks and exercises of communicative learning

technology considerably improved speaking, answering to questions, describing a text, asking a question, and understanding familiar topic levels. Thus, we make sure that there is a change in grammatical, lexical and phonetic knowledge of students. In addition, we noted that experimental group students made an improvement in overall grades, specifically grammatical, lexical and phonetic levels, speaking, thinking and speaking skills better. Also, desire of students to do new exercises each time and to use interactive methods which allows them to express their ideas freely was found.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Humanization of education will develop an individuality of our future generation. The effective use of innovative processes is a main requirement of the modern world.

To sum up, interactive way of teaching plays a major role among education techniques. Giving new materials, different and interesting tasks depend on the organizational skills of the teacher. Regardless of the type of method each of them has own advantages and disadvantages. It can be noticed that interactive way of education has more advantages than disadvantages. Corresponding to the requirements of educational reform it is important to update the content of education and its structural system in schools.

This paper considered several ways of teaching methods that will help to develop different abilities of students such as decision making skills and speaking skills through informative activities and cognitive actions.

REFERENCES

- [1] "The Kazakh language in the polylingual world: problems and future," Astana, pp. 109-113, March 2013.
- [2] K. Kadasheva, "The method of teaching Kazakh language", Almaty: *Murager*, 2005, p90.
- [3] "The interactive teaching methods of Kazakh language as the second language", Astana: *Sankt-Petersburg*, 2013, pp. 6-10.
- [4] K. Kadasheva, "The theory of teaching of Kazakh language in foreign audience", Almaty: *Sardar*, 2008, pp. 116-117.
- [5] G. Toktamysova, "The ways of developing pupil's speaking skills through communicative teaching technologies", April 2012.

Samal Abzhanova is a Master of Philosophy. She was born in Almaty, (Kazakhstan) on the 5th of November in 1982. Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, Faculty of Philology, Almaty city, Republic of Kazakhstan (2000-2004); Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, MA course, Faculty of Philosophy and Politology, Almaty city, Republic of Kazakhstan (2004-2006) MA was earned in 2006. Her major field of study is Kazakh Rhetoric. She is a Kazakh Language Instructor of the Department of Kazakh language, Literature and Culture (Nazarbayev University, Astana, Kazakhstan).

Saule Mussabekova is a Master of Philology. She was born in Zhambyl, (Kazakhstan) on the 12th of September in 1982. Taraz State University named after al-Farabi, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Taraz city, Republic of Kazakhstan (1999-2004); Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, MA course, Faculty of Philology, Almaty city, Republic of Kazakhstan (2004-2006) MA was earned in 2006; Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, Post-Graduate Program, Faculty of Philology, Almaty city, Republic of Kazakhstan (2006-2008). Her major field of study is teaching Kazakh as a second language.

She worked as a teacher of English Language in Almaty college of Management (2005-2006) Then she worked as a Coordinator of Linguistic Group in IT-company in Almaty (2008-2011). She also worked as English Language Instructor in Kazakh National Technical university named after K. Satpayev, Almaty (2008-2011). She is a Kazakh Language Instructor of the Department of Kazakh language, Literature and Culture (Nazarbayev University, Astana, Kazakhstan).